

Teaching as Entertainment: An Examination of Effects

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In 1969, wrapped in good intentions, *Sesame Street* debuted on public television. It was revolutionary and served as preschool for many American children who, at the time, could not attend a real school for financial reasons. Operating as the televisual manifestation of President Lyndon Johnson's Head Start program, *Sesame Street* was designed to confront some of the challenges being addressed by the president's War on Poverty. Today, not only is *Sesame Street* still going strong, but it has morphed into various international incarnations, from Mexico and Sweden to Saudi Arabia and Germany. It is a cultural phenomenon and beloved by its millions of viewers. It is also deeply valued by educators, and its influence is felt throughout all levels of public schooling.

We want to be clear about the nature of our objections to the program. In a television landscape full of "reality" programming, 24-hour everything, and specials that dig into the worst excesses of human nature, it can be said that *Sesame Street* is one of the more worthwhile television endeavors. However, as social commentator and philosopher Neil Postman said in "Five Things We Need to Know About Technological Change," every advancement or technological development has an idea that lies at its center. This idea may be counter-productive or beneficial, but it is seldom ambivalent. What is the idea behind *Sesame Street*, and what subtle impact has this program had on the education landscape? Our contention is that *Sesame Street* has led to an increasing perception of education through the prism of entertainment, and that profound effects ensue from this perception.

In the annals of education, among the works of the great educators and the thinkers who have written about education, one generally discovers that in writings about what it means to be educated, to acquire knowledge, *entertainment* or *fun* is not mentioned. This is not a critique of the use of humor in education; humor can enhance student memorization. However, when we speak of such concepts as *entertainment* or *fun*, we are talking about the idea of *entertainment* for its own sake, without an academic tie-in. We are speaking of tools that are utilized in place of (either purposefully or de facto) more meaningful and impactful, more authentic methods. What should be taught and emphasized is anything that draws out the natural interest inherent in a subject to appeal to the natural curiosity inherent in the student. We see this phenomenon of conflating education with entertainment as a form of false engagement for two reasons: one, entertainment as teaching is counter-intuitive to the educational process in general; two,

entertainment as teaching infers that teaching and the acquisition of knowledge are, in and of themselves, not enough. The prevailing thought behind this assumption is that school and learning are boring, dry, and in desperate need of revitalization.

As a result of the technological and televisual changes brought about by *Sesame Street* and other factors, over the last several decades, a tide of entertainment-centered technological innovation has swept through the education system within the United States, and in doing so, it has revolutionized the profession. In its wake have been left questionable practices, a diluting of knowledge, and a perversion of purpose. With each frantic attempt to attract student attention, the student becomes further disconnected from and disenchanted with the knowledge being presented. With every effort to cater to how students operate outside of school via entertainment and technology, the worth of the knowledge presented inside of schools is further cheapened.

In this paper, we seek to identify the problems adherent in common educational practice and the ideas that serve as their basis. Though applicable throughout the curriculum, our narrative focuses on ideas and experiences that relate to our own classroom experiences in the liberal arts, specifically within the area of historical studies at the secondary level. While taking a critical approach in this commentary, we recognize that teaching is an art form, requiring a nuanced approach. This view in fact informs part of our critique of the conflation of education and entertainment.

1. Teaching as Entertainment

The infiltration of entertainment into education is pervasive, and teachers would be hard pressed to spend a day — even an hour — without encountering it. So where does the impact of *Sesame Street* fit in? Education and knowledge acquisition are given a very light treatment in elementary school. Within the realm of historical education we ourselves can recall at the core of elementary school experiences memories of the Thanksgiving play or of the history teacher who dressed up as George Washington. We could almost concede to this method in elementary schools, which conflates history with play-acting, were it not for the fact that the *games* and other *fun* activities carry on into the higher grades.

In the late elementary and middle school years, high-stakes testing requirements become intensified; the child must confront aspects of learning that, at least on the surface, are not fun. In fact, the confrontation between entertainment and achievement represents the central controversy for teachers during the middle years. Over the course of these years, students develop and change in many ways, filling various roles within the school and taking various approaches to their studies. However, there are two major directions students might go: one, they might swallow the testing paradigm, and constantly fret about their grades; or two, they might progressively lose interest in school and education altogether. Between these two bookends, we perceive a continuum; however, we would like to address these two major categories separately.

The former type of student comes across as frenetic and anxious. Not all of the “best” students are like this, but enough are to generalize about them. In middle school, these students become the overachievers, told by parents and teachers alike that their entire livelihood hinges on each and every day, each and every quiz and test. The worst part about it is that some of these kids — our “best” students — hate school. They are punching a clock and ticking boxes towards graduation, passage through a good university, and a job where they will earn six figures. These students are the product of one of the most cynical and destructive trends in our society: the monetization of education. Education is no longer about opening doors, but about feeding a specialization. There is no authentic engagement; the focus of the student is to meet the minimum requirements for graduation and (usually) to begin college. This is the pursuit of knowledge in its most base form.

The latter group also consists of victims of a lack of authentic engagement, but in a different way. One might think that the infusion of entertainment would enhance this group’s engagement. However, evidence from our own classrooms seems to indicate that entertainment-oriented lessons and approaches have an inverse relationship with academic interest and cognitive development. While the day-to-day endeavor of teaching this group of students centers on ensuring success on standardized tests, exposure to new ideas is rare because new ideas and concepts do not appear on tests.

The matriculation into high school only exacerbates the problems encountered by both groups of students. To be sure, students change, and the cauldron that is the middle school years has an impact on how the student approaches studies. However, the high school years represent the ossification of attitudes towards education that first materialize at the end of the elementary and middle school periods.

Therefore, it is in the last half of public schooling that entertainment as an educational tool becomes most impactful. Instead of intensifying as the students grow presumably more capable of increased demands, the learning experience becomes shallower. What does entertainment look like at the high school level? We have seen at least one teacher within each of the many schools where we have taught who conducts class as if it consisted of screenings of Masterpiece Theater. To be fair, there are many schools seeking to do away with movie watching in class — or at least watching the entire movie — but this prohibition has more to do with the length of the films rather than with the medium itself.

Proponents of increased technology in schools suggest that, in part, we are using resources to which the students most gravitate. It is often said that students today are visual learners, and such tools as films — as a part of our educators’ *toolbox* — are key to getting the students ‘into’ the material. The problem is that such strategies, devices, or *tools* are created within an entertainment paradigm, not an educational one. Perhaps a video snippet could give the students a taste of a topic, but certainly it cannot serve as a substitute for reading, studying, and seeking to understand. We support John Dewey’s warning that it is *not* a teacher’s task “to make things interesting” (23). Instead, the teacher should begin with the student’s intrinsic interest, and “carry forward,” bringing

that interest into new domains (34). What would ‘making something interesting’ look like anyway? Some history teachers tend to expound upon student questioning to connect student ideas to events that occur at a later date or that occurred at an earlier time, or else to link student ideas to current events. Even if the questioning does not connect with the timeline being discussed, a thoughtful teacher can still address a query while maintaining the lesson for the day.

Students in Advanced Placement history classes are perhaps very smart and capable, but many of these students are unwilling to break out of their surface-oriented approach to the class. For these students, various “funny” online U.S. history videos teach the basics. However, this approach, in lieu of their reading the text, only helps them address some multiple choice questions. When students are asked to demonstrate their knowledge by way of an essay, many struggle mightily to accomplish the task. The average AP student in history has only taken in the course content at an informational level. As a result, the student cannot demonstrate substantial evidence of his or her knowledge of the subject through providing context, nuance, and interpretation, as often occurs in writing an essay.

And then, there is the History Channel. The issue with the History Channel is not unlike the issue pertaining to *Sesame Street*. Where the latter created a gross misinterpretation of how to approach education in general, the History Channel has done the same specifically for the subject of history. Like *Sesame Street*, it is not the fault of the creators of the History Channel how it is used and valued. Still, the viewer is expected to sit there and absorb, and nothing more is required. Then, the child is expected to treat history as the science it is.

Failing grades in history come as a bit of a shock — both to the student and to the parent. History is always a given. Nothing is pressed within this subject, which is considered *fun* and *easy* — so much so that the advanced students stop studying. Students in *regular* classes expect the same middle-school approach to continue in high school. However, when faced with even a scintilla of the discipline of history, some students struggle and fail. Parents email, saying, “I don’t know why little Johnny is failing. He always loved history — never made anything less than an ‘A’. He watches the History Channel all the time.”

While the above comments might seem irreverent in tone, we feel that entertainment in education has serious implications. Beyond history, entertainment has crept into every subject found in your local high school. In short, there is nothing wrong with the History Channel, or Bill Nye the Science Guy, or any of the myriad programming examples out there, *except* for their impact on scholarship and on the student’s ability to accept or understand the purpose of scholarship. The drive to find the easiest path has corrupted the learning process to the point that it will be difficult to reverse the trend.

Many teachers use such tools; but again, the assumption (or the fervent, cock-eyed, optimistic hope) is that the students are also reading. The students are not completely at fault, either, having been taught that the course grade, in the end, is the only thing that matters. Standardized tests have shown that knowledge is not what is important, but

rather than a narrow strip of skill sets and snippets of information suffices. Students are not ‘in the moment’ because they are not required to be — they are not authentically engaged because it is not necessary to *be* engaged in order to score the right grade or get into the right school.

Some of the questions that teachers often confront include, ‘*Will this be on the test?*’ ‘*How will it be graded?*’ ‘*What impact will this have on my overall grade or grade point average?*’ Not unlike a well-trained lawyer, the students are taking in the information as possible test fodder while the teacher is striving to underscore the authentic, interesting worth of the material. In a concept related to authentic engagement, the Buddha emphasized the importance of *right mindfulness*. Respected Vietnamese Buddhist monk Thich Nhat Hanh writes in his book *The Heart of Buddha’s Teaching* that mindfulness is about being in the moment. In moments of what Buddhists call *mere recognition*, “When we sit, we know we are sitting. When we stand, walk or lie down, we know we are standing, walking or lying down” (Hanh 69). In writing about his first travels through Yosemite Valley, famed naturalist John Muir noted his focus on every rock, every flower and every tree. He declared that while in a city, “I am a captive, I am bound” (qtd. in Badè 110). Yet walking through one of the natural wonders of North America, his mindfulness of the moment set him free. He was no longer restrained and blinded by the din of city life but set free by being able to fully focus on the here and now. While Hanh and Muir articulate a deep involvement in the moment, our students appear to be jumping ahead — *always already* leveraging the extrinsic value of their academic endeavor without considering its intrinsic worth.

2. The Opposite End of the Spectrum: The Hard School

In the 1973 film *The Paper Chase*, based upon the 1971 book by John Jay Osborn, Jr., first-year Harvard law student James Hart encounters the legendary Professor Kingsfield, a formidable educator and practitioner of the Socratic Method. He is the embodiment of what can be termed *the hard school*. The film opens with Dr. Kingsfield randomly calling on Hart to state the facts of the assigned case — a case that Hart has not yet read, since he was expecting a mere *overview* of the course. Rejecting Hart’s initial excuses, Dr. Kingsfield follows up relentlessly as the first-year law student flounders in front of his peers. Showing no pity, Professor Kingsfield presses Hart with questions that go beyond the details of the case, asking him to respond to a hypothetical example to draw out a fundamental point of law.

After this painful public emasculation during his first class in law school, and after Hart races to the bathroom to lose his lunch, the plot of the film takes an interesting turn. While the fellow students gossip about how Kingsfield took down another first-year law student, Hart gathers himself and systematically rebuilds his confidence. He later joins a study group, preparing relentlessly, extending lessons to include independent research, with special attention to archival writings by Kingsfield himself. Joining the “upper echelon” of students in Kingsfield’s contract law class, Hart volunteers to answer questions, engaging publicly with the famed professor, while others cower in the back of the lecture hall.

Worth noting is the closing scene of the film, where Hart receives his final grade for Kingsfield's contract law course. The viewer sees the professor placing a 93 on Hart's final examination, indicating a resounding success and his most meaningful academic accomplishment. However, in a twist of dramatic irony, the viewer sees Hart on the beach receiving his report card from a friend. Instead of opening the sealed envelope, Hart turns it into a paper airplane and throws it out over the ocean, never viewing its contents. While this perplexing response may cause discomfort in the audience of today, the director's intention was most likely to show that Hart had no interest in the numerical grade at all. For him, learning the fundamentals of contract law, overcoming his fear of public failure, and to some extent overcoming his fear of Dr. Kingsfield, transcended the value of any report card. For Hart, whose last name stems from the German word for "hard," the actual grade was irrelevant.

This example of the *hard school* approach may seem a little out of place in today's educational culture. In the present-day high school classroom, a student who is not prepared for a class discussion can typically downplay the oversight, make an excuse, or just admit to a lack of preparation. In most cases, the teacher will take pity, move on, and call on the usual suspects — students who *do* prepare — and this will provide the teacher with an easy transition, avoiding prolongation of an uncomfortable moment. However, based upon our time in the classroom, we wonder if avoiding public embarrassment actually benefits a student in the long run. We wonder if there is a time in a student's life when students require a hard school, a line in the sand that requires force of will to overcome a genuine challenge.

Cultivation of *will* would appear to be antithetical to current educational practice, particularly in the K-12 setting. While recognizing the irony of exemplifying educational rigor through a film designed primarily as *entertainment*, in the above discussion we draw out an educational contrast in terms of both style and substance. While we seek to highlight differences between *education as entertainment* and what we term *the hard school*, we recognize a continuum of approaches that resists categories. The best educators can move seamlessly along this continuum, providing students with humor, entertainment, structure, and challenge as appropriate. In keeping with the image of *cultivation*, one can think back to the German term *Bildung*, which resists translation. While representing *education* in general, *Bildung* has also been associated with the terms *image* [das Bild], *development*, *transformation*, and *growth*. Although Goethe's elaboration of *Bildung* in the context of cultivation of plant life is often cited, a rarer, though no less appropriate, source, also from the Enlightenment, is Immanuel Kant's *On Education* [*Über Pädagogik*], where Kant writes, using the auricula, a type of alpine primrose, as analogue:

when raised from a root this plant bears flowers of one colour only; when raised from seed, the flowers are of the most varied colours. Nature has placed these manifold germs in the plant, and their development is only a question of proper sowing and planting. Thus it is with man. (9)

While Kant’s analogy characterizes education as “only a question of proper sowing and planting,” he also implicitly recognizes a proper time for strict discipline — namely, while children are young and require “nurturing,” well before they are ready for scholarly pursuits.

Also implicit in Kant’s analogy is the need for different approaches to education at different periods of a child’s life. Particularly during the formative years, Kant indicates, nurturing may often, though not always, require discipline [*Zucht*] and will [*Wille*]. Nietzsche writes extensively on the cultivation of will, often within the context of education. Some of his posthumous writings detail his approach to schooling, including his observation that “The most desirable thing is still under all circumstances a hard discipline *at the proper time*, i.e., at that age at which it still makes one proud to see that much is demanded of one” (482).

While Nietzsche did not explicitly state *when* within a child’s educational journey *the proper time* would be to experience the *hard* school, we expect he had in mind a progression in which expectations and challenge increase as the child matures. Nietzsche’s conception of the will to power as the ability to obey internal commands is enigmatic to the extent that it supports inner causation — a process that can be refined and hardened through suffering. In concrete terms, the individual “commands” to the extent that he or she forms internal goals, while paradoxically also serving as the being who “obeys” those internal commands. Nietzsche clarified this point:

this is what distinguishes the hard school as a good school from all others: that much is demanded; and sternly demanded; that the good, even the exceptional, is demanded as the norm; that praise is rare, that indulgence is nonexistent; that blame is apportioned sharply, objectively, without regard for talent or antecedents. (482)

Tying the theoretical in with the practical is exemplified by Leiden University in the Netherlands. One of the more famous sites within the school is *het Zweetkamertje*, or the “Sweat Room.” The room was used as a waiting area before students proclaimed and defended their knowledge in front of a panel of professors. Approaching the room, two charcoal drawings can be seen on either side of a single wooden door. On one side is a depiction of a nervous student, worried about his future and sweating over the possibility of failing his exam. On the other side of the door is a depiction of an exuberant graduate skipping out of the room. Above the door is Dante’s warning from his *Divine Comedy*, “*Lasciate ogni speranza; voi ch’entrate* [Abandon hope all ye who enter here].”

Inside, where only a single desk sits at the center of the room, are walls covered by signatures of graduates who managed to pass their examinations and then signed their names to mark their time spent in this otherwise small, unremarkable room. Among the more noted luminaries whose signatures adorn the walls are those of Queen Beatrix of the Netherlands, Dutch resistance fighter Erik Hazelhoff Roelfzema, Sir Winston Churchill, and Nelson Mandela. While a recent restoration has highlighted the more famous signatures, the room and the experience associated with it were great equalizers. It was

not *whose name* was on the wall, but rather *what had been endured* and accomplished to justify the signature, that mattered.

The bareness of the room focuses the attention, in a way reminiscent of the Spartan room within Wartburg Castle where Luther translated the New Testament into German. There is nothing for the waiting student to think about or be distracted by. To stand in the middle of this room, to see the thousands upon thousands of signatures of graduates, the famous and not so famous, but who each sought to make a mark after such a shared tribulation, is indeed an awe-inspiring experience. However, the imagery conjured up by the room's name, considering the standards of today's public high school experience, presents a terrifying notion — in two key ways. One, we do not levy such assessments; and two, even if we did, we do not demand from students the ability to explain their knowledge, i.e., to contextualize it, to interpret it, to pursue it in depth. Ironically, the name *Leiden* is a derivative of the Dutch and German verb “to suffer.” But the suffering experienced in Leiden University's Sweat Room is not the type of suffering that leaves us, at the end of the day, covered in boils and considering our own mortality. Rather, suffering in this context provides the means to achieve a purposeful life, and stands at the opposite end of the easy and the trivial.

Students often look back on their high school career and harken back to that single teacher who made strict demands, who pushed them beyond their preconceived limits. The teacher's lack of pity could be described as generosity to the extent that he or she is investing in the student's ability to overcome and persist, often through strict adherence to rigorous academic standards. This is an issue that extends beyond our classrooms or any one discipline or grade. What we are discussing is a system-wide re-examination of how we educate our students. We are proposing a system that, from the beginning, does not apologize for content learned, but highlights the importance and the inherent interest of every subject and endeavor. Methodology will vary depending upon the age of the student, but the progression will ensure an increase of *intellectual stamina*. Throughout the public education experience, there must be an increasing demand placed on the student — not the fabricated demands of test scores and AP exams, but rather a demand that focuses on skills that supersede the capricious nature of current industrial and *real world* requirements. The student must be capable of a greater amount of sustained and productive study and learning.

3. Practical Implications: Operationalizing the Hard School

What we suggest is not easy for either the student or the teacher. We may attempt to run our class in the way it should be run, but we are working in isolation. From the onset, students must see school and the classroom as a gateway to understanding the world. A natural curiosity exists within each person, as is evidenced by a two-year-old's obsession with grass in all of its manifestations. We are born inquisitive people, and education must be a vehicle through which this curiosity is magnified and nurtured, not suppressed and destroyed.

In the book *The Once and Future King* by T.H. White, the magician Merlyn gives advice to a young Arthur about the importance of learning:

“The best thing for being sad,” replied Merlyn, beginning to puff and blow, “is to learn something. That is the only thing that never fails. You may grow old and trembling in your anatomies, you may lie awake at night listening to the disorder of your veins, you may miss your only love, you may see the world about you devastated by evil lunatics, or know your honour trampled in the sewers of baser minds. There is only one thing for it then — to learn. Learn why the world wags and what wags it. That is the only thing which the mind can never exhaust, never alienate, never be tortured by, never fear or distrust, and never dream of regretting. Learning is the thing for you.” (185-186)

Historically, places of worship have been sanctuaries, in an ecclesiastical sense as well as a practical one. Our classrooms should also be sanctuaries, indeed the *sanctum sanctorum*. Currently, cell phones, tablets, laptops, online surveys, online responses shown on a screen, online quizzes and tests, online textbooks and the like create a din that hampers attention and focus on the part of the students. In their 2009 commentary on experimental studies of deep reading, Maryanne Wolf and Mirit Barzillai found that, while online reading can offer a litany of information that greatly enhances reading, often it serves as a distraction and creates a skimming that prevents authentic, internalized comprehension. To use Heideggerian language, the classroom should be a place of refuge or a *clearing* where students can escape the hectic and superficial world outside the walls of the school to focus on the essence of that world with which few are in contact. Throughout history, voices in the wilderness have called upon us to focus on the nature of learning. In 19th-century America, transcendentalists Ralph Waldo Emerson and Henry David Thoreau suggested that society in general, and technology in particular, was corrupting. On this topic, Thoreau stated with regard to “modern improvements,”

there is an illusion about them; there is not always a positive advance....
Our inventions are wont to be pretty toys, which distract our attention from serious things. They are but improved means to an unimproved end, an end which it was already but too easy to arrive at (67)

While we are not ascetics, we believe there is value in putting aside the distractions and the noise in order to focus attention and attempt to understand the world.

At the center of the learning experience are three vital and integrated components: reading, discussion, and questioning. All societies built on learning hold the acquisition of knowledge, and discussion about and questioning of what is known and what is not known, as key tenets. Any reform of the modern American education system must include these three ideas as fundamental building blocks of the classroom. The 20th-century Austrian philosopher Otto Neurath narrowed this even further, saying that the essential building blocks of education are discussion and argument, to allow the student to differentiate in the process of argumentation the fundamentals and the ancillaries (Cat).

The form this focus will take will look different depending on the discipline, but these traits are at the core.

Still, this is not the easiest path. In many ways, people are wired to seek the easiest, simplest path — the shortest distance between point A and point B. It is our nature. But as with many other things that come to individuals naturally, education can allow us to take a path that is more rewarding and stimulating. In education, as American theologian and philosopher Abraham Heschel originally posited with regards to religion, what is rational and what is appropriate must bend the will — which always seeks the easier road. Educators must ask, as Heschel does, “what is the power that will make me love to do what I ought to do” (260)? Educators must lead their students to this question, as they also have the responsibility to try to answer it themselves and to stand against what is simple and (sometimes consequently) degrading. Historically, and contrary to any earlier assertion, we as a people are also capable of excelling when we toil in the shadows, and not in the light. The history of the United States is replete with examples of how Americans have risen to new heights through adversity: the war of independence against the British, the Civil War, the Great Depression, and World War II, as well as the fight for equality through various civil rights movements, to name a few examples. This is not only an American trait, but a human one, and one that should be applied within the classroom as well.

As teachers, we embrace the necessity of engaging the student, but the method typically employed is not authentic. Many students today have been weaned on an ethos that values finding the short-cuts, the tricks, the tips, the angles in being educated. While in pursuit of these approaches, students may expend a tremendous amount of energy, time and effort; however, they do so under false pretense. To confuse such an expenditure of energy with the true pursuit of learning undermines the value of that effort. Simply stated, the students’ effort is misplaced. The difference lies years down the road. Such an approach offers only the illusion of knowledge; what we are here discussing is simply the acquisition of information. Despite the current dogma uttered like mantras in public schools today, the acquisition of knowledge and the gathering of information are not the same.

Proponents of the use of entertainment or of other like educational methods do not value knowledge for its own sake but promote a debasement of knowledge to something as banal as information gathering. In our devotion to the gods of technology and entertainment, we are sacrificing the basis of what should be the pursuit of knowledge. We also monetize, and in the process, devalue what it means to be educated. Worst of all, the adults who are created by this method are less than what they could be. In Plato’s *Phaedrus*, in the context of the written word, Socrates criticizes the use of “external written characters” in the learning process, suggesting that such use creates a “semblance of truth” rather than true knowledge. Plato’s voice can be heard bemoaning the infiltration of technology into palaces of learning when he suggests that “[students] will appear to be omniscient and will generally know nothing; they will be tiresome company, having the show of wisdom without the reality.”

From our experience, teachers who employ the severe approach of Professor Kingsfield are conspicuous for their absence. We have seen rampant grade inflation and coddling of students by our well-intentioned colleagues throughout our teaching careers. Most teachers are well aware of the perfect storm of complaint they will receive when they award a student an 89% rather than following the standard practice of *kicking it up* to a 90% at the end of a grading period. Complaints come from all directions, including the student, parent, counselor, vice principal, coach, and often fellow teachers. Only the most self-possessed teacher can hold up against such opposition.

Following Postman's contentions in *Teaching as a Conserving Activity*, we support the conserving and criticizing function of education: education's "aim at all times is to make visible the prevailing biases of a culture and then, by employing whatever philosophies of education are available, to oppose them" (*Teaching* 20). To embody this concept, we need to take steps toward the hard school model. By acquiescing to the frivolous and counter-productive inclinations of modern educational thinking, we, as Aesop warned, provide the means of our own destruction. We recognize that our argument could be characterized as a step backward, particularly by those who seek to draw students into academic content by means of entertainment. It is our point that the "fun" is a product of the work — that when a student is tasked with investigating and reading about a subject, interest will build.

Nietzsche wrote that only the discipline of suffering is responsible for the achievements of man thus far. Thus we propose to interject into the classroom the creation of not some medieval torture chamber, but an oasis for study, reflection, conversation, and knowledge. In doing so, not only will we create an educated, confident individual, but we will also create a person who is increasingly capable of dealing with the challenges that lie ahead. With respect to the long-term education of our children, and in contrast to educational policy that champions something one day and discards it a couple of years later, Martin Buber declared that our primary concern should always be "the person as a whole, both in the actuality in which he lives before you now and in his possibilities, what he can become" (123). The future is where our motivation and duty as educators lie.¹

The idea behind Buber's words looms large in the modern education system — again, though, because it is made conspicuous by its absence. Parents and teachers alike know their actions have long-lasting implications when they are raising and educating a child. To that point, what parents and teachers understand suggests a level of awareness that is not possessed by school districts. Much of what takes place in public schools today is designed to address or appeal to the "right now." School, district, and state administrators seek immediate redress in situations where students' high-stakes assessments are unsatisfactory and reflect badly on the administration's ability to ensure education for all students. These evaluations are not just political, but ultimately economic in nature, affecting grants, programs, and general funding. The political sphere has never been a patient one, and the steps politicians and school administrators take show a haphazard and short-sighted approach.

That does not mean that such institutions do not recognize the importance of long-term considerations — in words if not in deeds. Nearly every school district (and school) has a mission statement, which invariably includes the empty concept of creating “lifelong learners.” There is very little in the messages of district administrators that promotes lifelong learning. The best hope for such a development lies with individual teachers who are able to establish genuine teacher-student relationships that build on the interest inherent in the subject. Yet from an administrative point of view, the focus is on the here and now.

Our industry sabotages the future in various ways. When we, as components in a system, focus on the end result — the grade on the test or on the report card — we undermine the importance of the process of learning. When one considers the overall approach toward education today, which holds that education is something achieved or accomplished, one realizes that we are teaching the idea that there is a conclusion to learning. If there is an idea more antithetical to the creation of lifelong learners, we are not sure where it exists. When we tie the school experience to what is obtained at university or in the workplace, we undermine the importance of knowledge for its own sake. When we focus our processes on technology and entertainment in order to make education more fun or easier, we undermine and trivialize what it means to become knowledgeable and wise.

Entertainment as a teaching tool, intentional or not, does not set the mind free to learn. It increases the noise and distraction; it erodes the attention. We have enabled a collective attention deficit disorder in our students, and made it worse by asking no questions about the impact of entertainment and technology within our sacred learning spaces. What the students need is authentic engagement — a real relationship with the knowledge we want them to seek and to hold dear.

Notes

¹ The authors would like to clarify what could be interpreted as conflicting or mutually exclusive statements. Earlier, we argued that students are distracted and tend to dwell ahead of themselves with respect to their academic activities. Our impression is that students have become increasingly focused on the instrumental value of their schooling; that is, students engage in learning activities for the contingent reward (grade, recognition, scholarship, praise) that is so overtly connected. At the same time, we state here that “the future is where our motivation and duty lie.” Here we are speaking not about students, but about educators who need to take a long view toward the intellectual, social, and moral development of their students. Thus, we hold that it is the duty of a teacher to ensure the comprehension of curricular content here and now, but also to develop within students an intellectual foundation that will sustain them in college and beyond, when the trappings of elementary and high school, along with the contingent rewards, may not be present. To further clarify, we suggest a need for students to become immersed in learning activities on a daily basis, so as to provide cumulative validation that learning as an activity is intrinsically valuable. At the same time, we suggest a nuanced approach for teachers, who must dwell in the learning moment with students, but also project possibilities for a deeper meaning for the learning that may only become beneficial in the distant future, beyond the standardized assessments, beyond college entrance exams, beyond job applications. In this way, we suggest that teaching and learning are sacred tasks with profound implications.

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